

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Darou-nansam**FIRST NAME:** Yasser**PROGRAM CODE:** DCCS**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author Xdid did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author Xdid did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 7%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Plagiarism does not occur when an author uses:

- A source of information without mentioning it.
- The words of a source without quotation marks.
- Information about common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.¹**
- Ideas from a source without footnoting.

2. Apply Direct quotations can be marked as follows:

- For four or fewer quoted lines, run them into your text, surrounded by quotation marks, and for five or more lines, set them off as an indented block.²**
- For four or fewer quoted lines, set them off as an indented block, and for five or more lines, run them into your text, surrounded by quotation marks.
- For all quoted lines, set them off as an indented block.
- For all quoted lines, run them into your text, surrounded by quotation marks.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 37.

² Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 77.

3. The preparation of academic and scientific documents requires mastery of the use of graphic forms. Which of the following graphic forms is best described?
- A Bar chart, grouped or split, compares two variables, with one segmented into ranges that function like the cases in a bar graph.
 - A histogram compares the value of one variable divided into two or more subsets across a series of cases.
 - A line graph compares continuous variables for one or more cases (e.g., temperature variable and viscosity variable in two fluid cases).³**
 - A Bubble chart shows the value of one or more variables for cases displayed on a map, diagram, or other image (e.g., states cases colored red or blue to show voting patterns variable).
4. Which of the following sentences describes a notes-style citation?
- In notes-style citation, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) beside your reference.
 - A notes-style citation is only used for scientific articles.
 - A notes-style citation is used when the sources for the notes come from the Internet.
 - A notes-style citation is used by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote or refer to it and then citing the source of that quotation in a correspondingly numbered note that provides information about the source (author, title, and facts of publication) plus relevant page numbers.⁴**
5. Journals are scientific or professional periodicals available mainly from university libraries and by subscription. Which of the following four statements is true?
- Journals correspond to magazines in that they are intended for a more general readership.

³ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 103-105.

⁴ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 141-143.

- Journal articles and magazine articles are cited in the same way, including dates and page numbers.
 - Articles in magazines are cited much like journal articles, but dates and page numbers are treated differently.⁵**
 - Magazine articles are cited completely differently from journal articles, as page numbers are not considered.
6. There are a variety of sources of potential bias in dissertation research. Among these biases, we have funding bias, which results:
- From the perceived efficacy of specific constructs used to conceptualize human development, personality, and service delivery intervention.
 - From personal experience, using interventions in practice leading to perceptions of the perceived effectiveness or ineffectiveness of a specific strategy of service delivery intervention.
 - From the need to justify obtaining or maintaining funding for a product, service, or other research project.⁶**
 - From the need to justify establishing, maintaining, changing, or eliminating one or more public policies.
7. Which of the following structures is recommended for a doctoral thesis?
- Title, Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (Review of the Literature), Chapter 3 (Method), Chapter 4 (Findings), Chapter 5 (Discussion), References, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, and Appendices of the dissertation.
 - Title, Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (Findings), Chapter 3 (Method), Chapter 4 (Review of the Literature), Chapter 5 (Discussion), References, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, and Appendices of the dissertation.

⁵ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 150-155.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017) 15-16.

- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (Review of the Literature), Chapter 3 (Method), Chapter 4 (Findings), Chapter 5 (Discussion), References, and Appendices of the dissertation.**⁷
- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (Review of the Literature), Chapter 3 (Method), Chapter 4 (Discussion), Chapter 5 (Findings), References, and Appendices of the dissertation.
8. The statement of the problem is a succinct statement of the dilemma that the research questions are intended to resolve. There are no literature citations in the statement of the problem because:
- Relevant key cites have already been provided in the presentation of key elements preceding the paragraph on the statement of the problem.**⁸
- The problem statement does not address either gaps in the content of previous research or problems with the methods used.
- The citations in scientific research concern only the literature review.
- The citations cannot in any way guide the problem statement.
9. Data analysis techniques are used to answer the research questions or to test the hypotheses that are derived from the research questions. Using valid data analysis techniques is critical in conducting valid research. There are two elements of data analysis validity: congruence and accuracy. these two elements are described as follows:
- Accuracy* involves providing a rationale that shows how the data analysis method for both quantitative and qualitative research fits the questions being asked or the hypotheses being examined. Description of the rationale for using various data

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 20.

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 28.

analysis methods helps the reader determine if the analytical techniques are appropriate for the research design and the measures used to represent the variables in the dissertation. *Congruence* involves providing evidence that the analytical techniques used in the research provide correct answers to the research questions being asked or the hypotheses being posed. Establishing the accuracy of data analysis helps the reader to judge whether or not the findings obtained in the dissertation can be trusted.

- Congruence* involves providing a rationale that shows how the data analysis method for both quantitative and qualitative research fits the questions being asked or the hypotheses being examined. Description of the rationale for using various data analysis methods helps the reader determine if the analytical techniques are appropriate for the research design and the measures used to represent the variables in the dissertation. *Accuracy* involves providing evidence that the analytical techniques used in the research provide correct answers to the research questions being asked or the hypotheses being posed. Establishing the accuracy of data analysis helps the reader to judge whether or not the findings obtained in the dissertation can be trusted.⁹**
- Congruence involves providing evidence that the data reduction and analytical techniques used are correct. The citations in scientific research concern only the literature review. Accuracy involves providing a rationale that shows how the data analysis method for both quantitative and qualitative research fits the questions being asked or the hypotheses being examined.
- Congruence and accuracy involve providing evidence that the analytical techniques used in the research provide correct answers to the research questions being asked or the hypotheses being posed.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 47-48.

10. Punctuation in English text must follow English rules and conventions, which often differ from those that apply to other languages. Which of the following punctuation is correctly described?
- Use question marks to identify words and phrases that are not themselves quotes but to which you wish to draw attention as lexical items.
 - Use a colon rather than a semicolon to combine two sentences into one without a linking conjunction.
 - A semicolon is most often used to indicate that an expansion, qualification, quotation or explanation is about to follow (e.g. a list of items in running text). The part before the semicolon must be a full sentence in its own right, but the second need not be.
 - A full stop marks the end of a sentence. All footnotes end with a period, with the exception of those consisting solely of an Internet or e-mail address. Do not use a period at the end of a title.¹⁰**

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Commission 2021) 7-13.

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